

Rac-3d

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-116-rac-20%AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	xt10113
Vial:	80	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 116 rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	13.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/11/2021 10:15:33 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/12/2021 5:09:38 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.362	967798	50.28	79984
2	10.825	957002	49.72	51741

Asy-3d (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-117-4-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	35	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 117 4
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	13.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/13/2021 4:45:48 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/13/2021 5:00:24 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.321	384416	4.09	31752
2	10.769	9007648	95.91	484970

Asy-3d (KR)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	x1-2-117-3-20%AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	x10113
Vial:	79	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	x1 2 117 3
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	13.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/11/2021 9:56:45 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/12/2021 5:08:08 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.360	193280	2.56	15837
2	10.820	7343080	97.44	396731